

HORIZON EUROPE

Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the Green Deal

HYPERIMAGE

A universal spectral imaging sensor platform for industry, agriculture, and autonomous driving.

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= Deliverable D9.1 = **Initial Communication Kit**

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HyperImage

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 9.1. Initial Communication Kit is part of task 9.1 Dissemination and communication activities, which ensures the results of the project will be disseminated to the European research and industrial community and will be communicated to the general public, the scientific community, technicians, experts, media, policymakers, industries, end-users, and other stakeholders. The initial communication kit of the HyperImage is a set of promotional materials aimed to inform the wider public about the project, its objectives, and its expected impact. The package includes HyperImage (1) logo, (2) leaflet, (3) and webpage. In addition, the social media account of the project is presented.

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1. Introduction

Deliverable D9.1 is associated with task T9.1 – “Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation of the project’s outcomes”. The objective of this deliverable is to present that the results of the project will be disseminated to the European research and industrial community, will target all important stakeholders, and will assure an ongoing communication flow with the general public, the scientific community, technicians, experts, media, policymakers, industries, end-users.

The aim is to present promotional materials and distributed widely in all key events and through a regularly updated database of contacts. Social media will also be used to reach a broader audience. Moreover, the document includes the creation of a dedicated website for the project, presenting comprehensive information about the project visually and interactively. This public website is created at the beginning of the project and will be actively maintained during the whole implementation.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. HyperImage Logo

The project logo was prepared by an AMIRES/ABIMI designer and proposed three options for the Project Coordinator (IWS) and WP9 leader (ABIMI) to establish a visual identity for the project and its consortium. The logo is used in all project-related communication materials, websites, leaflets, posters, and brochures as well as internal document templates and confidential materials.

The logo is inspired by the RGB colours and spectral concept of the image layers. Firstly, the idea was a cube with images layers in RGB colour. However, to be more modern it was chosen a black font industrial, therefore the cube was elongated in horizontal orientation as the currently version in Figure 1. The logo was presented and approved by all partners at the project kick-off meeting held on 16th and 17th January 2024. All files referred to the logo package can be found in project SharePoint¹, such as the logo colourful, black&white, and in high-quality.

Figure 1: HyperImage Logo

2.2. Project Image

During the proposal stage, a schematic (Figure 2) was developed to illustrate the central concept of the project. This schematic delineates the primary technologies that the consortium will contribute, including innovative modular photonic components, high-performance spectral image sensors, industry-suited spectral image sensing systems, and innovative spectral image analysis software solutions. Furthermore, it outlines the diverse range of applications for these technologies, encompassing autonomous off-road vehicles, unmanned aerial vehicles, automated indoor farming, and quality control in semiconductor processing.

Figure 2: Scheme during proposal stage - overall concept of HyperImage project.

¹ Available at [HyperImage logo Package](#) (request access)

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However, the image (Figure 2) is a technical and not attractive to be display in the dissemination & communication materials. For this reason, a project image was designed with the objective of the reader to see the image and understand the key elements of the project.

In Figure 3 is possible to observe the logo of the project with the grey spectral which reaches the project logo that contains main methodological technologic such as software solutions, sensors and photonic instruments. The inputs is a polychromatic spectrum going out from the logo and presenting the main HyperImage application, which are unmanned aerial vehicles, automated indoor farming, autonomous off-road vehicles and quality control in semiconductor processing.

Figure 3: Project image: an updated version to be displayed in the dissemination materials.

2.3. HyperImage leaflet

The project leaflet (Figure 4) is a short print material to provide a brief overview of the project in an attractive text, to make the reader curious to learn more and visit the project's social media and website. It's summarized the overview, goals, impacts, and partners briefly to those interested in the topic.

The leaflet can be distributed at conferences, events and on the premises of the partners. The leaflet provides acknowledgement of EU funding and includes the EU emblem.

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Figure 4: HyperImage leaflet.

2.4. HyperImage Roll-Up

The Roll-up (Figure 5) will be present in the main events and meetings. The background image is standard to all communication materials and is presented and matches the logo's colours. The roll-up is focused on the project name and disseminating the website, also serves as a background for pictures during the project's meetings.

Figure 5: HyperImage Roll-Up

2.5. First press release

In the second month of the project, a press release announcing the successful launch was published in the main page of the Fraunhofer IWS website. The press release titled "A Universal Spectral Imaging Sensor Platform for Industry, Agriculture and Autonomous Driving" is available and the target public is the research society. The authors describe that HyperImage project, aiming to create a versatile spectral imaging sensor platform for industries like

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agriculture, manufacturing, and autonomous driving. It plans to integrate innovative photonic components into cameras and use AI for data analysis. The technology will be validated in four areas, including autonomous driving and crop monitoring. Benefits include increased yield, reduced costs, and improved efficiency.

Figure 6: First press release at Fraunhofer IWS website.

2.6. HyperImage Website

At M2 of the project period, the primary webpage was published with general information about the project and its partners. The preliminary page (Figure 7) contains the project logo, abstract and the partners list. It was created as a preliminary version in case the visitors would like to have more information about the project.

Figure 7: Primary HyperImage Website.

As soon as the domain address www.hyperimage-project.eu was saved the preliminary page was set-up. However, a new design, layout, has been developed. The website development and maintenance are led by ABIMI.

The purpose of the HyperImage website is to achieve the following objectives:

- To be a digital “business card” for partners, highlighting mission, members, and opportunities for those who want to learn more about the trends within spectral image technology.

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- To relay timely information about the project developments, events, and results.
- To create a digital contact mechanism for those who wish to contact the team.
- To allow interested parties to follow the LinkedIn page of the project, to attract more followers for regular communication in related fields.

The website layout has received approval from both the coordinator and the dissemination manager. The subsequent phase involves the coding process, to be executed by ABIMI designer at *WordPress*. Upon completion of the website development, content creation will undergo a thorough review by both beneficiaries. This is why the content in the figures below appears blurry; the coordinator and dissemination manager will review it meticulously to prevent any potential misinformation.

The homepage, (Figure 8), will mirror the content found in the leaflet (Figure 4), offering a concise project overview alongside crucial details such as partner count, participating countries, duration, and budget. The menu bar will maintain a clean appearance, featuring easily accessible submenus. Under the "Project" tab, visitors can explore the project's impact and ambition. The "Results" section will house public deliverables and publications, while the "Newsroom" will provide access to press releases, media resources, and LinkedIn feed interface.

For the mobile version it will appear the project image (Figure 3) without the figures from the applications industries, however for the desktop version by the project image (Figure 8) it will be available images related to the application. For each application described in the project image the end-users partners provided their images to be displayed. These images will not only enhance the visual appeal of our website but also provide visitors with a clear depiction of the various applications of HyperImage.

Therefore, figures was requested to the following partners:

- Unmanned aerial vehicles (NEO)
- Automated indoor farming (Growy)
- Autonomous off-road vehicles (ROB)
- Quality control in semiconductor processing (IFBIP)

Figure 8: HyperImage website - homepage layout.

As mentioned, the project tab will have submenu as the project ambition and impact, it will be a concise page to explain to the visitor the main objectives and novelty of the HyperImage and the impact that is expected (Figure 9).

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Figure 9: HyperImage website - Project ambition and impact page

Following the menu in the home page the next tab is to present the partners, for that will be allocated the pictures of each beneficiary's team (Figure 10). Moreover, the visitor can click in the partners and will be redirected to the partners website to be able to learn more about them and provide network within the consortium for future collaborations.

Figure 10: HyperImage website - partner's page

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The results (Figure 11) will be allocated for the public deliverables, such as this one and future publications. In the other section can be allocated poster or results form the conferences, seminars and other presentations that contributed to the project’s dissemination.

Figure 11: HyperImage Website - Results page

The last page is the contact us (Figure 12). The messages will be redirected to the coordinator and project manager

Figure 12: HyperImage website - Contact us

The website will be updated recently even after 5 years after the termination of the project. In the footnote there is a acknowledge to the EU, respectively: *HyperImage Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe – The EU research & innovation programme under the Grant Agreement number 101135827.*

3. Conclusions

This document represents the Deliverable D9.1 Initial Communication Kit. It includes the first promotional materials for the HyperImage project to create awareness and inform the wide and various target audiences about the HyperImage project and its development. These materials will be extensively used by partners whenever they present at conferences, publish in journals and magazines, establish contacts with media, attend exhibitions, organize workshops, etc. The materials will be revised over the course of the project to integrate the project results as they are produced. Moreover, the communication kit will be expanded to include project presentations, videos, and others, with additional communication means considered on a running basis.

When disseminating the results of the HyperImage project, the following sentence, alongside the EU emblem, will always be included: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101135827. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

The dissemination of the project's achievements should never jeopardize the potential protection of generated intellectual property and further industrial application. Therefore, before any dissemination activity (publication, presentation) strict rules of prior notice to all partners will be applied, according to EC guidelines and HyperImage Consortium Agreement: prior notice of any planned publication should be given to other consortium members at least 45 calendar days before the publication. The Dissemination Manager (Marina de Souza Faria - ABIMI) will follow the approval processes and will act as an internal executive approval body for any dissemination/exploitation action organized by different partners.

4. Degree of Progress

Degree of fulfilment of the task activities respect of what reported in the DoA.

5. Dissemination Level

This deliverables is public.